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Teaching-Learning Practices during Pre-and-Post-Covid-19 Pandemic Lockdown: An Analytical Study

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Abstract: The Covid-19 pandemic put nations, regions, educational institutions, and people at risk. Because of continuous lockdown, schools were forced to modify their teaching methods and the learning support provided at home. This study sought to provide understanding on how teaching methods in education changed between the first and second pandemic lockdowns. According to the previous research's, there was a considerable decline in the quantity of help given at home for schoolwork and extracurricular activities between the two lockdowns, as well as in how much time students spent on watching TV-broadcast lectures and receiving family-supported reading instructions. A significant increase in the amount of time students spend in independent reading activities and in teacher-guided reading instructions. In the second lockdown, there were more synchronous lessons taught by a teacher and more synchronous sessions where students practiced in reading. Additionally, parents felt more capable of assisting their children in learning to read during the second lockout and thought synchronous lectures were more helpful at improving their children's reading abilities. These findings on the basis of secondary data are used to talk about how schools responded to the Covid-19 Pandemic and how online teaching and learning was done.

Keywords: Covid-19, Education, Lockdown, Online Teaching, Parents, Students

1.1 Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has caused abrupt and profound changes around the world. The longest school closings paired with a coming recession and an unparalleled interruption in education had caused the largest shock to educational systems in decades. Governments all throughout the world suspended face-to-face instruction in schools to slow the spread and evolution of the pandemic, affecting almost 95% of students worldwide (United Nations, 2020).

It seems to have generally caused a severe impact on education among students and especially in higher education, as they were in the middle of their even semesters and the lockdown imposed on them, led to a shift in their learning methods. However, it is also undeniably true that these students were unable to work one-on-one with their teachers because of the pandemic, which caused all educational facilities to be shut-down immediately. As a result, the transition from traditional classroom learning to computer-based learning became one of the biggest academic changes that the students had to adjust to. As a result, it aids in gaining a better grasp of the necessary educational reforms for pandemic and post-pandemic situations, as the latter necessitate considerable systemic change rather than waiting for normalcy.

2.1 Implementation of online teaching-learning

The implementation of the transformation process in the educational system that has emerged after the Covid-19 crisis has encountered various challenges; these challenges are connected to the innovative perspectives of online education and their technological complexity. Earlier to the pandemic, online education was considered as the education provided by the open universities in some parts of the world. Online teaching and learning, however, were a significant difficulty to manage during the Covid-19 induced period, and people were not technologically capable enough to adapt to the unexpected change in the educational system. Therefore, implications of change need to be addressed in order to successfully execute educational change (in this case, it refers to the switch from traditional teaching-learning techniques to online teaching-learning methods). The fundamental goal of teaching and learning in the pandemic setting was to preserve consistency in providing high-quality instruction. Unfortunately, the pandemic situation with the enforced lockdown had forced educational institutions to adopt online learning methods. However, previous studies have shown that students do not favour using technology like mobile phones to evaluate online education, even though they are necessary to handle such a crisis (Papadakis Education and Information Technologies- 2021). In order to clearly comprehend the efficacy of these strategies, it is necessary to analyse the usefulness of these novel concepts for distant learning. The goal of the current analytical study was to explain how educational teaching strategies altered between the first and second pandemic lockdowns. Gaining a greater understanding of how learners perceive web-assisted learning strategies could aid in their deployment and give consistency during these trying moments.

2.2 Teaching-learning during pre-and-post-covid-19 pandemic

The world of education after Covid-19 can be very different from what it was before. It is a well-known truth that education is one sector that has been severely impacted by the pandemic. Our lack of disaster readiness demonstrates the persistent wide-ranging inequity. Given our current access to computers and internet, this inequity may now be quantified (or do not have). Such inequality has exposed the public-private fault lines. In order to accommodate digital and distance learning, the commercial sector has demonstrated significantly greater resilience than the public one. This has actually widened the gap between learners within the span of one year. However, the online learning exposes us to a different form of privatisation. The school has relocated from its public spaces into private ones. The classroom atmosphere has changed, and the presence of students in their domestic space has created multiple psychosocial issues as well. The students at home have shifted the focus of education to a domestic sphere. Teachers have come to understand that education cannot be contained within the formal framework of a classroom. The presence of television, radio, and the internet has demonstrated the importance of the medium being adaptable and accommodating. However, the learn-from-home paradigm has transformed the parents into substitute teachers. The vertical relationship between

a teacher and a student has evolved into a horizontal one where new stakeholders and increased levels of participation are needed for the delivery of education. The financial crisis brought on by the epidemic will take years to recover from, and many students may struggle to find employment after they complete their study. It can even get to the point where the value of education itself is called into question. Despite all of these unknowns, the unpredictable stock market and decreased or non-existent funds from governmental agencies have a negative impact on university finances. Numerous small and medium-sized private institutions would suffer the most, and as a result of the unstable finances, they would finally close. The most affected sector remains higher education. Business schools are likewise not far from being impacted by the epidemic in the meantime. Some industries, like all of the service sectors, were instantly engulfed by Covid-19. Students who want to work in these fields now have to divert their attention to other fields. The government is making every effort to aid in the recovery of the economy and the populace from this crisis (Bolara, 2020). The reality is that the only sectors and organisations that can successfully move from a physical model of operations to an online one will survive this crisis. The companies must use a hybrid model of education, often known as a phygital mode (George, 2020), to meet all of these demands. Organizations, however, struggle to properly utilise the physical model. What can be the most efficient teaching methods from a physical perspective is the pressing concern here. The authors in this paper discuss some of the successful teaching strategies or techniques that all the educational institutions can use to succeed in these challenging times of the Covid-19 pandemic in relation to all these difficulties. The innovative teaching methods in the physical style would be interesting to observe. The Covid epidemic has been the subject of extensive research on both education and teaching.

The post-Covid-19 world required all businesses to undergo digital renovations. Although underdeveloped countries are also undergoing this digitalization, the pace of change has substantially accelerated since the outbreak (Gupta, 2020). The current educational methodology and learning approaches must be revised overnight due to the extraordinary circumstances of Covid-19 (Gupta, 2020a). It is necessary to change the current teaching and learning model to one that might benefit students by providing them an appropriate online learning experience, rather than, for instance, combining online and offline learning approaches (Roy, 2020). Although there are many online platforms offering various programmes with unique methodologies, evaluation results, and diplomas, what is required is an integrated learning system (Augustine, 2020). The number of students enrolling in online learning courses has been rising sharply, and this overall multiplying demand has been accelerated by a number of factors, including cost effectiveness, the flexibility of time and place, the opportunity to attend classes virtually, space for performing different wide and varied works of adult daily lives, and a decreased amount of distraction compared to face-to-face learning (Hannay et al, 2013). Despite an increase in online learners, online learning has always been associated with a variety of risks as well, including the absence of an instructor, a lack of peer contact compared to face-to-face learning, low motivation, inadequate time management, and a lack of individual learning capacities (Jaggars, 2013). In the post-Covid era, educators and students are compelled to use web-assisted learning tools including the internet, websites, telecommunication, radio, video recording, etc. for a variety of tasks like giving lectures, giving out study materials, and assigning homework (Masrom, 2007). It is much like face-to-face learning in which classroom teaching and live interactions between teachers and students take place, when both of them are online at a certain time to communicate directly with each other (Buzzetto-More, 2015). In several studies examining and contrasting student's perceptions of social presence, social interaction, and satisfaction with e-learning and traditional learning, it was discovered that while e-learning is perceived as lacking in social interaction, social presence, and efficient synchronised communication, it offers many advantages including convenience and ease of time, an easy understanding of important concepts and subjects, and opportunities for independent learning (Cuthrell et al, 2006). On the other hand, research like that conducted by Tratnik (2017) discovered that students enrolled in traditional courses of study had been in general more satisfied with a few select factors than the online learners. Kemp and Grieve

(2014) discovered that although academic achievement levels were comparable between the two approaches, undergraduate students preferred to complete tasks in person rather than online. Other studies claim that classroom dynamics and social interactions, which are crucial components of face-to-face regular learning, promote learning engagement and lead to more effective, fruitful, and meaningful learning (Hurst et al., 2013). Additionally, studies reveal that student's perceptions of online learning especially in higher education are significantly impacted by elements like age, gender, computer proficiency and technology tolerance, learning patterns, lack of awareness, interest, personal touch, and interaction because of connectivity issues (Arora & Srinivasan, 2020). Another study discovered that the majority of students favour online learning, although they feel that these courses are lacking in extracurricular activities (Lall and Singh, 2020). Since, face-to-face learning opportunities are affected by the pandemic; educational institutions took an alternative and complementary path of web-assisted online classes, providing learning opportunities for students (Nandakumar, 2020).

2.3 Objective of the Study

This study has sought to provide understanding on how teaching methods in education changed between the first and second pandemic lockdowns (pre-and-post-covid-19 pandemic lockdown).

3.1 Research Method

The entire study is based on reviewing of primary data sources (observations) as well as secondary sources of data such as; newspapers, official reports, previous articles as well as book chapters by keeping an objective that has sought to provide understanding on how teaching methods in education changed between the first and second pandemic lockdowns.

4.1 Conclusion

Covid-19 had a significant impact on the education system in a number of ways. The epidemic coincides with the rise in the potential of information technology. The result will probably be a reconfiguration of the information technology-based educational pedagogies. While the importance of the offline educational system cannot be discounted, mixed learning with an emphasis on online pivots and a digital attitude would be the way of the future. Several difficulties need to be addressed when we transition to an adoption technique for digital technology in teaching and learning. First, the development of an appropriate interface for learning and engagement compatible with the extant infrastructure is required, given the financial concerns of institutes discussed in the introduction. Second, the efforts need to be focused on advancing the use of technology in education. Third, the directions for successful experiential learning that may also improve student's skill sets and employability need to be established due to the constraints concerning internships that allowed business school students to learn in a real-world working environment. The fourth factor is parental involvement and support in raising their children. Last but not least, strategies to bridge the digital divide for inclusive education require rapid attention. In order to use blended learning successfully, a new paradigm that has been introduced by the Covid-19 pandemic needs to be explored. In addition, the use of online education is giving the learning community a sense of psychological protection throughout the Covid-19 crisis. The most important step is about changing process under which two options are left: either embrace a new online mode already being used by other institutions elsewhere, or develop one's own. Notably, change in this context occurs dynamically as a break in continuity rather than as an event. We need a new mentality and a time-appropriate outlook for online teaching

mode at the individual and organisational levels to support the transition phase for any result-oriented change (Bridges, 1991). Tam and El-Azar (2020) argued that “resilience must be integrated into our educational systems” and identified three trends that would characterise upcoming changes: an increase in educational innovation, a confidence in public-private educational partnerships, and the existence of a digital divide. After months of pre-Covid-19 online encounters, a paradigm shift in online education has taken place, gaining popularity to have/near permanency even during the post-Covid-19 pandemic that causes refreezing. Refreezing is a necessary step in incorporating technology into our teaching-learning process because it enables us to teach students using techniques that will not only make them feel at ease but also enable them to meet the demands of technology in the twenty-first century. Therefore, it is recommended that the academics should make extra efforts to improve the post-pandemic learning system. For instance, providing discussion time or practise sessions where students could engage in peer communication as well as allocating more time to improve effective communications with learners (using online/Google classrooms/Internet, etc.). They (the teachers and the student’s parents) ought to make an effort to encourage and urge students to engage in discussions with their peers about various subjects in order to enhance peer collaboration.

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